

NERSC Technical Report no. 403

ARCTIC MAPPING – ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRE APPLICATION

IMPLEMENTATION USING OPEN SOURCE FRAMEWORKS DJANGO REST AND WQ.IO

by

**Frode Monsen
Tor I. Olaussen
Florian Geyer
Hanne Sagen
Torill Hamre**

4 June 2020

	<p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) Thormøhlensgate 47 N-5006 Bergen, Norway Phone: + 47 55 20 58 00 Fax: + 47 55 20 58 01 E-mail: post@nersc.no http://www.nersc.no</p>
---	--

<p>TITLE: Arctic Mapping – Online questionnaire application Implementation using open source frameworks Django Rest and WQ.IO</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION: NERSC Technical Report 403</p>
<p>CLIENT: Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center</p>	<p>CONTRACT: Marine data i Arktis: Fra kartlegging til kunnskap (QZA-15/0137 - KLD40241) Marine data i Arktis (NERSC kompetanseoppbygging)</p>
<p>CLIENT REFERENCE:</p>	<p>AVAILABILITY: Public</p>
<p>INVESTIGATORS: Frode Monsen Tor I. Olaussen Florian Geyer Hanne Sagen Torill Hamre</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION:</p>
	<p>DATE: 4 June 2020</p>

SUMMARY: The INTAROS H2020 project defined a set of online questionnaires for surveying in situ observing systems in the Arctic, their data collections as well as remote sensing products and Community Based Monitoring (CBM) data. INTAROS conducted a survey among INTAROS partners and a limited number of external parties using a commercial tool, Google Forms. While the chosen tool made it easy to generate the online survey, several shortcomings were found. This included, among others, limited options for validating user input, lacking support for geographic locations and storage of responses in a flat file without versioning. The “Marine data in the Arctic” spin-off project builds on and extends the INTAROS questionnaires to provide a more flexible solution that also aggregates the collected information and presents it using various kinds of plots. With additional support from NERSC basic funding, we have developed an open source survey application that can form the backbone of an up to date inventory of Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. This report describes selected aspects of the new survey application – *ARC*MAP – and outlines potential enhancements to further improve its functionality and ease of use.

TABLE OF CONTENT:

Introduction	3
Short overview of WQ.IO	4
Creating web-pages with WQ.IO	5
Limitations in the WQ.IO framework	6
Extending WQ.IO to support multiple choice selection boxes	6
Other changes to the ARCMAP application	8
Statistical plots	9
Importing data from the INTAROS survey	10
Packaging and deploying the survey application	11
Future work	12
Appendix A : User Manual	13

1. Introduction

The INTAROS H2020 project defined a set of questionnaires for surveying in situ observing systems in the Arctic, their data collections as well as remote sensing products and Community Based Monitoring (CBM) data. These questionnaires were implemented using Google Forms, and a survey conducted among INTAROS partners and a limited amount of external parties. This survey resulted in descriptions of 58 in situ observing systems, and a total of some 180 data collections. While the chosen tool made it easy to generate the online survey, several shortcomings were found. This included, among others, limited options for validating user input, lacking support for geographic locations and storage of responses in a flat file without versioning. Thus, there was a need for developing a more flexible online survey application.

After a successful bid for the Arktis 2030 call for Arctic environmental protection projects issued by the for Norwegian Directorate for Climate and Environment, the project “Marine data in the Arctic: From mapping to knowledge” started 1 July 2018. This “Marine data in the Arctic” spin-off project builds on and extends the INTAROS questionnaires for in situ observing systems and their data collections, and will conduct a survey to capture information about in situ observing systems operated by Norwegian institutions that are not participating in INTAROS.

A specific objective of the “Marine data in the Arctic” project is to develop a new solution for the survey application allowing for easier entry and update of information from INTAROS questionnaires A and B (Figure 1). This solution should store the information in a database, to enable user defined statistics to be extracted on the fly from the survey. Developing tools for such user defined extraction of summaries and key aspects of the collected information is the second goal of the “Marine data in the Arctic” project.

Figure 1. Illustration of components of three of the INTAROS questionnaires.

The Arctic Mapping survey application – called *ARCMAP* – is developed using open source technologies: the [WQ.IO](#) web questionnaire framework on top of [Django REST framework](#). WQ.IO is a framework for implementing [XLSForms](#), a standard for creating and sharing forms in web-pages, using The Django REST

framework as a base. In addition, several JavaScript libraries are used for the front-end (i.e. graphical user interface) development.

The remainder of this report is organized as follows. Sections 2-7 describes selected aspects of the WQ.IO framework, with focus on specific challenges faced when developing *ARCMAP* and the solution found to provide easy to use and robust survey applications. Section 8 presents a few examples of aggregated statistics of the INTAROS survey results, presented as different types of plots that highlight the extracted information. Section 9 describes some of the challenges experienced when transforming INTAROS survey results from a flat text file to a relational database, the solutions found. Section 10 presents the technologies and tools used to package the *ARCMAP* application and deploy it to a public web server. To conclude the report, Section 11 outlines potential future work that will enhance the functionality of *ARCMAP* further.

2. Short overview of WQ.IO

WQ.IO is a web-framework that utilizes the Django Rest framework for back-end operations, and a variety of JavaScript modules for the front-end presentation. For template files WQ uses the Mustache logic-less templates, which is a method that uses templates with variables to be filled with data. First WQ creates the HTML template files from the Django model files using master template files, and secondly to import data from the database into the HTML templates.

There are two main sources for information about the WQ.IO framework.

1. WQ.IO documentation (the *Docs*) with high-level overview of the framework, links to projects using the framework and detailed descriptions of, among others, installation, configuration, templates and command line tools: <https://wq.io/1.1/docs>
2. A set of *example applications* built using WQ.IO: <https://github.com/powered-by-wq>

It is also possible to find some information from other projects that are using the framework, such as:

- <https://atlasbiowork.com/>
- <https://species.wq.io/reports/new>

However it is common for all the projects found that they have a single form page that incorporates a map with a few text fields. In addition, there may be a single choice selection field but no complex features. Two typical examples of use of WQ.IO are shown in Figure 2. To the left a plot of observations of bees within a user defined region. To the right an input form for registration of species observations, where the location (latitude, longitude) can be given by the user by either clicking on a map, using GPS from the computer/mobile or entering the coordinates manually in two text fields below the map.

Figure 2. Selected examples of WQ.IO usage from the North Dakota Bee Map project (<https://wq.io/projects/nd-bee-map#&ui-state=dialog>) and the Species Tracker (<https://species.wq.io/>).

3. Creating web-pages with WQ.IO

The WQ.IO has two methods for creating web-pages (Figure 3).

The first is “**addform**”.

This method gets the input directly from an Excel-workbook that is built according to the XLSForms standard¹, and first builds the default Django Rest back-end files, and then the HTML-templates and JavaScript front-end files.

This method allows for a multiselect front-end, but not on the back-end, and there is no possibility for manipulating the back-end files.

The second method is “**deploy**”.

This method does not read the Excel-workbook, but gets its input from the Django Rest back-end files. This means it is less compliant with the XLSForms standard, mostly because it does not have access to information that isn’t stored in the back-end files. However, there are also some seemingly unnecessary differences in the code, which may be due to the code of the deploy method being older.

This method makes it possible to manipulate the back-end files.

¹ <https://xlsform.org/en/>

Figure 3. Main steps when running the addform (left) and deploy (right) methods of WQ.IO.

Since the deploy method is less compliant with the XForms standard, we choose to manually update the HTML-templates before running the deploy method, and skipping that step when running the deploy-process.

4. Limitations in the WQ.IO framework

WQ.IO is a very good framework for getting started with a questionnaire that includes Geographic Information in maps. Because it automatically builds the necessary back-end and front-end files from information in an Excel sheet, and it is up and running after just a few adjustments.

However, it does not support all elements of the XLSForm definition.

Among the not supported elements are:

- Check-boxes (Multi-select).
- Selection Choices with possibilities of users adding a choice outside of the ones listed (or_other).
- Repetition.
- Groups with other fields than text in them.

5. Extending WQ.IO to support multiple choice selection boxes

Multi-selection fields are not mentioned anywhere in the WQ.IO Documentation. Thus, version 1.1 of WQ.IO did not support multiple choice questions.

In Django the standard method of implementing static multiple choice questions is to use the `django-multiselectfield` application or another similar application. However this and all other attempts to solve this issue with Django Rest are ignored by WQ.IO when building the front-end of the questionnaire. Thus, we had to pursue another approach to implement support for multi-select choices in WQ.IO.

The following steps have made a multi-select field possible on the front-end of ARCMAP.

- Creating a new Mustache template file for Check-boxes.
- Implementing that template in the `html-fields.html` Mustache file.

The code base of WQ.IO also had to be extended to handle multiple choice questions in ARCMAP. These changes included, among others:

- Implementing the `django-multiselectfield` application.
- add `'multiselectfield'`, to `INSTALLED APPS` in `base.py`
- In `models.py` import `multiselectfield` field, and set the multiple choice questions to type `multiselectfield.MultiSelectField`
- Adding a `serializer.py` file that implements the `rest_framework.fields.MultipleChoiceField` for the multi-select questions.

The extension for multiple-choice questions in ARCMAP could not be fully automated within the given time frame and available resources. One step remained manual:

- Adapting the HTML-files to the changes made to the back-end.

This also means that deployment of the web-page can no longer be allowed to update the HTML files.

Combined, the changes described above allow for the back-end to accept more than one selection to be made in questions of the ARCMAP survey application. However, there are still limitations. With these changes, the questionnaire does not accept the form if only one choice has been made in the multi-select question.

Additional changes were implemented to support for multi-choice questions in ARCMAP:

- In the back-end, create a `serializers` file for each form that has multi select questions, and put a subclass of the `rest_framework.fields.MultipleChoiceField` in it that converts string values into a list.

This enables the back-end to accept both single and multiple choices to be made in the checkbox questions.

- Modifying the `ModelSerializer` class in `serializers.py` in the `wq` library `add_lookups` function to compare each field in the model with any part of the response from the database, instead of it having to be an exact match.

This lets the web-pages accept more than one answer in the response from the database.

- Modifying the `BaseModelSerializer` class in `serializers.py` in the `wq` library by adding (`serializers.MultipleChoiceField`, `'select all that apply'`) to the `xlsform_types` variable

This makes it possible for the `deploy` function to identify multi select questions, and use the multi select Mustache file.

-
- modify site-packages/wq/app/js/wq/app.js to accept lists in the context of `_choice_label_lookup` and `_choice_dropdown_lookup`

This lets the web-page recognize that more than one choice has been made in multi-select questions.

6. Other changes to the ARCMAP application

ARCMAP organises a questionnaire as a set of web forms that are presented to the user in separate web pages, which can be edited and stored individually. Figure 4 shows the structure of Questionnaire A from the INTAROS survey. After a user has logged in, he can open earlier submissions and update these, or register new observation systems by creating new forms. ARCMAP links each observation system to the specific user that registered it.

Figure 4. Extract of ARCMAP home page showing structure of Questionnaire A.

Linking information to user accounts: For each form, the ARCMAP application holds the registered information in a Django model class. For instance, the information for form 1A is held by a class called `GeneralInformation`. In all the other model classes holding information for the other forms in Questionnaire AA, there needs to be a reference to the `GeneralInformation` class, allowing ARCMAP to identify the answers from the same user and observation system. This is done by setting a foreign key to `GeneralInformation` in the `models.py` source code file for each of the other forms.

Support for “or_other” option in questions: For all questions with an “or_other” option, we have added “other” as a choice, and added a text question right after it to put the extra information in, and we modified the HTML to not show the label of the text question.

Enhancing map component to improve usability when registering locations of an observation system: The file `rest.py` in `Locations` is updated by setting `marker`, `line` and `polygon` to `True`. The configuration in `App/js/arcmap/config.js` can be updated to let the map start with a better geographical area. We have chosen to set `bounds : [[61, -10], [84, 15]]` denoting a bounding box of 10W-15E, 61N-84N, to define a suitable area for ARCMAP.

The XForm definition of maps only supports maps that can store and show one type of measurement (point, trace or polygon). However, we need to support all three feature types for the same observation system, so the map type is changed to `GEOMETRY` in `models.py` and in the database.

To make this change in the database, a new version of the Location table must be created. The GEOMETRY field type is not officially supported in sqlite3 and as a result, migrations on the Location table no longer works, which means that this change and all future changes to the database for the Location form, has to be done manually.

To show the position on the pointer label when adding a point on the map, modify the leaflet.draw.js in the wq library (site-packages/wq/app/js/) set : `this._tooltip.updateContent({text: latlng.toString() });` in the `onMouseMove` function in the `L.Draw.Polyline` and `L.Draw.Marker` classes.

Use of ID fields to govern access to survey forms in ARCMAP:

In order to control who is given the rights to change information about each of the observing systems, we created ID fields in the General Information form that automatically obtain data about current user and original creation data (of the filled in form) when a new form is added.

The steps taken to add the ID fields are:

1. Create a view class for the GeneralInformation form that retrieves the information, and import it in `rest.py`,
2. Add information on how to store it in the database to `models.py` for the GeneralInformation form.

The other forms will have the access rights information available through a link to the GeneralInformation form that holds the ID fields for their observation system.

To hide information from other users, create a filter in `rest.py` for all forms that only downloads the records the user is allowed to see and/or edit.

Improve navigation through the different forms for an observation system: The next form buttons are added in the `_detail` html-templates for each form. This makes it easy for users to go to the next form in the questionnaire when registering an observation system.

7. Statistical plots

To show some statistics from the answers to Questionnaire A of ARCMAP, there are a selection of plots publicly available at <https://ci.nersc.no/client/plots>. The plots are updated every morning between 6 AM and 7 AM GMT.

Most of the plots are presented as .png image files, and are listed on the home page. A few plots are made as their own html pages, and are listed under the 'More Plots' item on the main menu.

Figure 5 shows some examples of plots generated by ARCMAP.

Figure 5. Examples of plots from ARCMAP: different aspects of maturity for the registered observation systems (left), overview of variables measured (upper right) and distribution of respondents by country (lower right).

8. Importing data from the INTAROS survey

The original INTAROS survey was stored in a single Excel spreadsheet per questionnaire. Each line in the spreadsheet held one response from the survey, and when responses were updated only the latest version could be held with limited possibilities for ensuring the stored data were valid. Thus, we decided to change to a database solution to remedy these problems. A Python script was written to convert the spreadsheet to a SQLite/Spatialite database. A combination of import tools (spatialite-gui/SQLAlchemy) and Structured Query Language (SQL) queries were used to import and convert the data.

When designing the new Django/WQ.IO-based system we split the questionnaire into six main parts:

- DataManagement
- DataUsage
- GeneralInformation
- Location
- ObservationsImpact
- Sustainability

To accommodate the new layout, the original data had to be split into corresponding six tables in the database (representing Django models). Two new fields were created to keep each respondent's answers together. The first extra field was the internal WQ.IO record ID, and the second was a corresponding foreign key (quesa_id) to keep related records together. In addition, all the positional data needed to be converted; latitude and longitude coordinates needed to be switched to fit the representation of geographic locations in

the new system. This was accomplished using SQL queries within a SQL tool. The original Excel data was essentially rows and columns of unformatted text data. There were several issues regarding the formatting of this text data, specifically with regard to dates and multiline, quoted data. The dates could for the most part be handled through standard date conversion routines in Python, while nested, quoted text blocks would often lead to the shift of data columns where data would be imported incorrectly. Regular expressions and filtering of special characters and nested quotes of text took care of most of these cases. In a few difficult cases, the data was manually corrected in the final system, when audited. In conclusion, after multiple iterations, we ended up with a combination of Python scripts and SQL-queries within GUI tools to complete the import, with a final audit in the completed system when all the data had been added.

In this way, we were able to import the old data into the new Django-based system without having to make any special accommodations within the new system. After the final import and conversion, all corrections and additions are made in the new system. Based on the work done here, a streamlined import method can be generalized for use with the other questionnaires.

9. Packaging and deploying the survey application

To facilitate a common environment for development and deployment, the complete Django/WQ.IO system was first installed into a Docker container. This makes it possible to move the whole system intact to various computers and servers.

A virtual server, ci.nersc.no, was created with only a web server and the base Docker system installed. The Docker container is moved to this server as a Docker image, which is represented as a single file that contains everything needed to run the DjangoWQ.IO system. The Docker image is imported and started on ci.nersc.no. The web server is configured as a proxy to make it publicly available as shown in Figure 6. The database with all the data is stored outside the Docker container for continuity purposes.

Figure 6. Illustration of the ARCMAP architecture that shows the relationship between the main server, web server, Docker container with ARCMAP system and database to store the data. The user connects to <https://ci.nersc.no> with a standard web browser, the web server handles the user's request and acts as a proxy to communicate directly with the ARCMAP system within the Docker container. The Docker container handles the connection to the external database.

In addition, a source code repository has been created on gitlab.com and configured to support continuous delivery/continuous integration (CD/CI) which will simplify future development when taken in use.

The server ci.nersc.no functions as a survey system and a data repository. The surveys are available through the standard web-based forms interface, and the data is made available through an API (Application Programming Interface). The surveys as well as the API are secured through user authentication and can be made available to licensed external users. This makes the Django/WQ.IO system extremely flexible and able to integrate with external systems to avoid data duplication.

10. Future work

The ARCMAP system opens up several avenues for future development of different applications and services. Users can be national authorities using environmental observations in their assessments and policy making, research funding agencies and ministries for planning of future monitoring programs and research strategies. To extend the functionality and make it more robust and interoperable with other similar systems, we propose the following developments.

Improved registration of platform and sensor locations. An observing system can consist of a sizable number of fixed or moving platforms and sensors. The current version of ARCMAP supports registration of multiple locations, including combinations of points, lines and polygons, but all locations must be given by positioning a cursor on a map in the browser. Extending ARCMAP to allow users to give positions in text fields can make the registration of positions more user friendly. WQ.IO has a module that we may be able to adapt for our purposes and extend it to support multi-point and line features for locations of platforms and sensors.

Optimised structure of the database including data collections. The questionnaires in INTAROS for data collections are complex and demanding to fill in. In ARCMAP we propose to link the data collections directly to a component (e.g. platform or individual instrument) the Observing System and simplify the registration process in a more schematic way allowing for populating of information about data collections.

Visualisation of Observing System locations and categories. A dynamic map component for visualising the location of observation systems and their parameters will enable users to quickly get an overview of which variables are being measured in different regions and time periods. The basic mapping of locations will be implemented using an open source mapping library, such as OpenLayers. Additional filtering functionality needs to be developed to enable users to investigate the changes in parameters being measured in different time periods and within different domains (e.g. oceanography, acoustics, biogeochemistry, species).

Develop Analysis tools to extract information from the questionnaire e.g

1. Calculate operationality scores: the system's ability to provide data in real time into a data system with standard formats.
2. Filtering capabilities with respect to a selection of parameters e.g. years, categories, platforms, country, geographical location, and visualize on geographical map and other graphics and tables.

Exchange with other data and observing assets systems. Data infrastructures such as the Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC) and Norwegian Scientific Data Network (NorDataNet) have extensive catalogues with detailed descriptions (metadata) of marine data collections. By harvesting metadata from such catalogues, ARCMAP will be able to populate part of the data collection descriptions (Questionnaire B), such as location, time period, parameters measured, what data formats and data access protocols are offered. This will reduce the amount of manual registration substantially, and be far easier to update. The SIOS Observation Facility Catalogue and the Arctic Observing Viewer are two examples of observation assets systems holding descriptions of observation systems and their components that are highly relevant for ARCMAP. SIOS development is based on the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS)

metadata standard for collection of meteorological and related environmental observations. Extending ARCMAP to support WIGOS will enable mutual exchange of assets descriptions with SIOS, and may also serve as a testbed for exchange with other assets systems.

Extend ARCMAP to include registration and assessment of Data Systems and Community Based Monitoring. These are important components of the Integrated Arctic Observing System. The next step after identifying CBM data systems will be to investigate the possibilities for exchange of data on observing assets and data collections with ARCMAP. Inclusion of CBM will impose restrictions on access and use of data in case of sensitive information. Data systems will in particular be assessed by parameters describing user friendliness for upstream and downstream services.

Extend ARCMAP database with Russian and Chinese observation assets. Establishing international collaboration by including assessments of observing systems provided by the Russian and Chinese partners of INTAROS, This will include opening for registration in ARCMAP; and work to set up exchange of data with existing Russian and Chinese data and observing facility systems.

Appendix A : User Manual

ARCMAP User Manual as of May 2020

Updates to the user manual will be posted on the ARCMAP web site at <https://ci.nersec.no/>

User Manual ARCMAP

ARCMAP is an online application for collecting and updating information about in situ observation systems. This enables the user to create and edit detailed descriptions of observational systems that are, have been or are planned to measure various environmental parameters in the Arctic. Observation system information is organized in a database so that it can be easily retrieved and updated, or used in the analysis of the environmental monitoring capacity for a given area and time period. Each user has access to the data they have registered. Administrators and customer / client (eg Ministry of Climate and Environment (KLD), Environment Directorate (MD)) have access to information about all registered systems and to extract new statistics and indicators.

ARCMAP is available at <https://ci.nersc.no/>.

There are four methods for retrieving information from ARCMAP:

- 1) automatically generated figures with overview data that is updated every day (open access)
- 2) access to questions and answers in the questionnaires (user account)
- 3) installation of client application with tailor-made presentation (needs user account)
- 4) direct data download from database (needs developer account)

1. Automatically generated figures with overview data (open access)

A number of overview figures are automatically generated and updated every day. These are publicly available at <https://ci.nersc.no/client/plots.html>. The figures cover a number of themes from the ARCMAP database (see Figure 1). Feedback about additional overview figures is welcome so that we can post more figures that are useful for monitoring developments and uncovering gaps in the observation systems. An overview map showing all registered observation systems is under development; this will also be posted at <https://ci.nersc.no/client/plots.html>.

Figure 1. Two simple examples of extracting information from the ARCMAP database: which application areas the observation system serves (top) and overview of how many systems measure given parameters (bottom).

2. Access to questions and answers in the questionnaires (need user account)

Users, customers and administrators can log in on the main page <https://ci.nersc.no/>. Ordinary users will then see all the observation systems that they themselves have added into the system. They can create new observation systems or update the information for their existing observation systems. Users can see all the questions that underlie the ARCMAP system, and they can see their own answers to these questions. However, they do not have access to other users' observation systems.

Customers have read access to all observation systems. This way they can look at all the metadata collected in ARCMAP.

Administrators have full read and write access to all observation systems. They can also create accounts for new users.

The figure consists of three screenshots from the ARCMAP application:

- Top Screenshot:** A map titled "Tine Larsen-GLISN network Greenland-GLISN". It shows a map of Greenland with several blue location pins. To the left of the map is a table with the following content:

Reference to the General Information page	Tine Larsen-GLISN network Greenland
Spatial coverage: name of location	GLISN
*Spatial coverage: Enter a point location, a line or an area.	Locations with multiple points
*Temporal coverage - Start date	1930-01-01
Temporal coverage - End date	
- Middle-Left Screenshot:** The "arcmap" login page. It features a "Log In" button and a menu for "Questionnaire A: ARCTIC EXISTING IN SITU OBSERVING SYSTEMS". The menu items are:
 - 1A. GENERAL INFORMATION ON THE OBSERVING SYSTEM AND THE RESPONDENT
 - 1B. LOCATION INFORMATION
 2. OBSERVATIONS AND POTENTIAL ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT
 3. SUSTAINABILITY OF THE OBSERVING SYSTEM
 4. DATA USAGE
 5. DATA MANAGEMENT
- Middle-Right Screenshot:** The "Edit Questionnaire A: 4. DATA USAGE" form. It includes a dropdown for "Reference to 1A General Information" (set to "Hanne Sagen-Fram Strait Multipurpose Acoustic System"). Below this are several sections:
 - Category of the observation network/system:**
 - Broad network (it includes a broad range of interdisciplinary observations and projects)
 - Focused network (is confined to specific themes or disciplines)
 - Commercial network (provide observational data for profit)
 - Operational network (feeding data into weather service and forecasting entities)
 - Resource-extraction network (conducts monitoring or baseline observations specifically for planned or ongoing resource extraction activities)
 - Distributed data (from many local networks)
 - Application areas:**
 - Climate Research and monitoring
 - Process oriented research
 - Research supporting operational services
 - Operational services
 - Climate services
 - Public exploitation
 - Commercial exploitation
 - Environmental assessment
 - Risk assessment
 - Other:

Figure 2. Selected screens from the ARCMAP application: overview of locations for land-based stations in a glacier monitoring network in Greenland (top), the front of the application (bottom left) and the applications of one of the marine observation systems from the INTAROS survey (bottom) right).

3. Installing client application with tailor made presentation (need developer account)

An example of a standalone client application that can be customized and installed on a local website is also created.

The client has no special requirements other than a user account and network access, and reads the data from ARCMAP:

ARCMAP Client Home Charts Account

Questionnaire Summary

Login

Username

Password:

[Login](#)

You can view raw data tables:

ARCMAP Client Home Charts Account

Questionnaire Summary

ID	DOMAIN	CATEGORY	OWNER
13	atmosphere	atmosphere_surface_layer	
14	atmosphere	atmosphere_surface_layer	
15	land_including_terrestrial_cryosphere	terr cryo_greenland	
16	land_including_terrestrial_cryosphere atmosphere	terr cryo_greenland atmosphere_surface_layer	
17	land_including_terrestrial_cryosphere atmosphere	terr cryo_snow atmosphere_surface_layer terr cryo_glaciers	
18	land_including_terrestrial_cryosphere	land_seismic_stations	
19	land_including_terrestrial_cryosphere	land_surface_atmosphere_fluxes	
20	land_including_terrestrial_cryosphere	terr cryo_glaciers	

And plots:

Questionnaire Summary

This client make it possible to integrate ARCMAP in its own environment with its own data, while the data remains in the main ARCMAP system. This avoids duplication of data.

4. Direct data download from the database (needs developer account)

The frameworks on which ARCMAP is based, Django2 and WQ.IO, offer extraction of data from the database through a built-in interface (API). This makes the data available for further processing. The automatically generated figure presented under point 1 shows examples of some forms of analysis possible with the metadata in ARCMAP. The web page with the automatically generated plots uses the data retrieval APIs and generates presentations that are dynamically updated as users update the information in the database.

This kind of direct data access is made available to customers and service developers. With this, they will have the opportunity to create their own overview figures and analyzes based on the metadata in the ARCMAP database.